

A Comparative Observational Study of Feto-Maternal Outcomes between Pregnancies in Women <19yrs V/S Pregnancies in Women >30yrsSuman Rani¹, Vasudha Rani², Puja Mahaseth³¹Junior Resident, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, 846001²Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, 846001³Associate Professor & HOD, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, 846001

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** The objective of this study was to document the number of pregnancies in women aged ≤ 19 and ≥ 30 years, at a tertiary care hospital, to compare social characteristics such as religion, education, occupation, and contraceptive use between the two age groups. Additionally, the study examined the incidence of anemia, pre-eclampsia, and gestational diabetes in both groups during pregnancy, as well as differences in delivery mode, birth weight, and fetal outcomes.**Methods:** This prospective study, conducted at Darbhanga Medical College from September 2022 to February 2024, compares maternal and neonatal outcomes in 100 pregnant women aged ≤ 19 and ≥ 30 years using comprehensive statistical analysis.**Results:** The study found no significant differences in marital status (82% vs. 96%, $p=0.238$), rural residency (76% vs. 64%, $p=0.255$), hemoglobin levels (8.78 ± 1.09 vs. 9.44 ± 1.7 g/dL, $p=0.213$), or cesarean delivery rates (74% vs. 48%, $p=0.865$) between pregnant women under 19 and over 30 years. Eclampsia incidence was higher in older women (10% vs. 4%, $p=0.008$). Neonatal deaths (14% vs. 4%, $p=0.24$) and low birth weights (50% vs. 36%, $p=0.247$) were more common in younger women, though these differences were not statistically significant.**Conclusion:** Women aged ≤ 19 require more attention to prevent preterm births and improve neonatal outcomes, while women aged ≥ 30 need monitoring for gestational hypertension and diabetes. The study also concluded that pregnant women over 30 had a higher incidence of eclampsia, while those under 19 experienced more neonatal deaths and low birth weights. Although these trends were observed, other factors like marital status, rural residency, and cesarean delivery rates showed no significant differences between the two age groups.**Keywords:** Feto-maternal, Maternal age, Eclampsia, Neonatal outcomes, Low birth weight.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Maternal age is a key factor in optimal reproductive health, with high-risk groups being women under 19 or over 30. Adolescence, defined as ages 10 to 19, marks the transition to reproductive maturity and adulthood. This phase is stressful, and pregnancy during this time is considered high risk. In India, early marriage has been a tradition, with census data showing an average marriage age of 13 for females before 1951.

However, by 1978, the Child Marriage Restriction Act raised the legal marriage age from 15 to 18. By 1998, the average age of marriage had risen to 19.5 years in many states. The age at which a female marries and becomes sexually active affects fertility. Girls marrying before 18 tend to have more

children. In India, 65% of teens aged 17-19 are either pregnant or already mothers. Raising the marriage age to 20-21 could potentially reduce births by 20-30% [3]. High rates of adolescent pregnancies are due to factors such as early marriage, societal norms, low literacy, lack of sexual education, and limited contraception.

Adolescent pregnancies carry heightened risks due to the young age of the mother, with increased chances of complications like pre-eclampsia, anemia, and preterm labor, leading to higher perinatal morbidity and mortality [4]. Women aged 30 or older who become pregnant face additional risks, requiring special care due to increased maternal and perinatal complications [6, 7]. Over the past 30

years, delaying childbirth until after 30 has become more common, partly due to the rise in reproductive technologies [8], societal shifts, increased participation of women in the workforce, and higher education attainment [9]. Reliable contraception and various infertility treatments have contributed to the growing number of pregnancies among women over 30, despite the associated risks [10, 11].

Since 1950, advanced maternal age has been defined by Waters and Wagen as 35 years or older. In industrialized nations, delayed childbirth has become increasingly common due to women's focus on education, careers, and delayed marriage, alongside the availability of reproductive treatments [12]. According to the CDC, between 1990 and 2012, the birth rate for women aged 40-44 more than tripled, reflecting changing family planning and reproductive health trends [13].

Pregnancies in women over 35 tend to have more complications than in younger women, including hypertension, diabetes, preterm delivery, and low birth weight. Delayed pregnancy increases risks of complications like pre-eclampsia, fetal growth problems, and higher rates of instrumental births and caesarean sections. Newborns are also at higher risk for premature birth, abnormal positioning, and requiring NICU admission due to perinatal illness and death [14-17].

While global research has addressed adolescent pregnancies, studies focusing on India's unique socioeconomic structure are limited. Tertiary care hospital patients in India tend to be older due to better socioeconomic standing. This study focuses on comparing the outcomes of pregnancies in women at both extremes of the age spectrum to assess their impact on maternal and newborn health outcomes.

Materials and Methods

Type and place of Study

This study adopts a prospective, comparative case study design, aiming to evaluate and compare various maternal and neonatal outcomes between two distinct age groups: ≤ 19 years and ≥ 30 years.

The research is conducted within the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital (DMCH), Laheriasarai. This hospital serves a diverse catchment population, predominantly comprising lower middle-class families residing in the vicinity of the hospital, residents from neighboring districts, and a portion of slum dwellers. With an average annual delivery rate ranging between 500 to 600, the hospital provides a significant sample size for the study.

Period of Study

September 2022 to February 2024, encompassing a

total duration of 18 months. This extended timeline facilitates the collection of comprehensive data, capturing variations in outcomes across different seasons and periods.

Inclusion Criteria

Healthy pregnant mothers ≤ 19 years and ≥ 30 years, regardless of their parity, who are attending the antenatal clinic at DMCH.

Exclusion Criteria

Pregnant plus pre-existing medical disorders that could potentially influence pregnancy outcomes are excluded from the study such as:

- Bronchial asthma
- Hypothyroidism, or a history of poor obstetric outcomes.
- Pre-existing diabetes mellitus
- Heart or kidney disease
- Chronic hypertension

Sample Size

100 pregnant women with 50 pregnancies < 19 years and another 50 pregnancies ≥ 30 years. This sample size is chosen to ensure adequate representation of both age groups and to facilitate meaningful statistical comparisons.

Sample Procedure:

1. Pregnant women meeting the inclusion criteria are identified and recruited from the Antenatal Clinic of Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital.
2. For each participant, a prepared and printed proforma, containing relevant parameters for data collection, is completed during each antenatal visit throughout the pregnancy.
3. Each proforma is serially numbered, and the same number is recorded on the top right-hand corner of the patient's antenatal card for identification purposes.
4. Detailed medical histories, including demographic, socio-economic, marital, and reproductive information, along with past medical records and investigations, are documented.
5. Antenatal examinations of the mother, including physical examinations and relevant investigations, are conducted and recorded.
6. Following delivery, the proforma is updated with relevant details, including mode of delivery, maternal complications, and neonatal outcomes.
7. Regular monitoring of the indoor wards is conducted to identify patients admitted for delivery on days outside the regular clinic schedule, ensuring comprehensive data collection.
8. Parity, education, employment, use of contraceptives, prenatal care, hemoglobin levels, blood pressure, blood sugar levels (fasting), among the various factors assessed for women

and infants are abnormalities at birth, preterm, jaundice, and neonatal mortality.

- Daily examinations of mothers and newborns continue until discharge from the hospital, with any complications noted and documented.

Statistical Analysis

Data are organized in Excel and analyzed using SPSS 27.0 and GraphPad Prism 5.0 to investigate the impact of maternal age on pregnancy and child-birth outcomes, highlighting differences between age groups.

Results

The study examined various obstetric parameters, comparing pregnant women under 19 years with

those over 30 years. Maternal age ranged widely across the two groups, with notable differences observed in gravidity, as all pregnant women under 19 years were primigravidas compared to only 4% in the older age group.

Blood pressure upon admission, marital status, rural residency, and hemoglobin levels showed diverse ranges across both groups without significant differences.

However, eclampsia incidence was notably higher among women over 30 years. Other obstetric factors such as liquor AFI, premature rupture of membranes, and mode of delivery varied without significant distinctions between the two age groups (Table 3.1 & 3.2).

Table 1: Sociodemographic and obstetrical outcomes of study women (n=16)

Parameter	Women <19yrs, n=50	Women >30yrs, n=50	p value
Maternal age (years)	16.82±1.42	33.6±2.49	0.589
Gravida G1	50 (100%)	02 (4%)	0.00006
Systolic blood pressure upon admission (mmHg)	163.40±16.7 [10]	144.40±24.5 [35]	0.62
Diastolic blood pressure upon admission (mmHg)	87.60±14.9 [5]	96.50±9.3 [40]	0.804
Cohabiting with partner (Marital Status)	41 (82%)	48 (96%)	0.238
Rural residency	76%	64%	0.255
Hemoglobin upon admission to labor (g/dL)	8.78±1.09	9.44±1.7	0.213
Eclampsia	2 (4%)	5 (10%)	0.008
Pedal edema+Ascitis	7 (14%)	5 (10%)	
PIH	2(4%)	4 (8%)	
PPH	0	4 (8%)	
Proteinuria	30 (60%)	27 (54%)	
Proteinuria+S.Creatinine+LFT/KFT deranged	2(4%)	2 (4%)	
Proteinuria+Secondary PPH	5(10%)	3 (6%)	
Primary PPH	2(4%)	0	0.282
Liquor AFI (clear)	31	26	
Liquor AFI (Meconium)	19	24	
Premature rupture of membranes before admission	33	26	0.624
Delivery by cesarean section	37	24	0.865

*p-value determined by Student's t-test.

Table 2: Neonatal outcome

Parameters	Women <19yrs, n=50	Women >30yrs, n=50	P value
Fetal heart rate (per min)	121±6.63	124.96±8.66	0.883
Gestational age (weeks)	37.02±1.23	36.7±1.96	0.897
Weight (kg)	37 [2]	37 [2]	0.247
Neonatal deaths	7 (14%)	2 (4%)	0.24
Length (cm)	49.4±0.83	49±2.07	0.113
Preterm	18 (36%)	20 (40%)	0.193
Small for GA	12 (24%)	2 (4%)	0.39
Low birth weight (<2,500 g)	25 (50%)	18 (36%)	0.247
Apgar <7 at first minute	7.06±1.09	7.12±1.04	0.00001
Admissions to neonatal intensive care unit	25 (50%)	21(42%)	0.493
Artificial Rupture of Membranes	20 (40%)	40 (80%)	0.647
Asphyxia	6 (12%)	10 (20%)	0.84

*p-value determined by Student's t-test.

The data on sociodemographic outcomes (Table 3.1) highlight some interesting trends between the two groups. In terms of marital status, 82% of women under 19 were cohabiting with their partner compared to 96% of women over 30, but this difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.238$). Rural residency was slightly more common among younger women (76% vs. 64%), though this also lacked statistical significance ($p=0.255$).

These figures suggest that younger pregnant women may face different social circumstances, but these do not seem to strongly influence pregnancy outcomes directly. All cases in the dataset of

Women <19yrs group are primigravida (G1), indicating that these women are experiencing their first pregnancy (Figure 3.1). Gravida values are primarily G1 (indicating the first pregnancy) in both age groups.

Women <19yrs group have a low mean (0.33 and 0.125 resp.) and median (1) for gravida, indicating a low number of pregnancies (Figure 4a). Gravida 2+ is Multigravida, where a woman who has been pregnant more than once, regardless of the outcomes of those pregnancies. In the group, Women >30yrs group gravida 2+ with different conditions were observed.

Figure 1: (a) Distribution of Gravida (G1) in both age group cases; and (b) Distribution of multiple Gravida (2+) in Women >30yrs group

In terms of obstetric complications, there were notable differences between the age groups. Younger women had a higher prevalence of pedal edema with ascites (14% vs. 10%) and were more likely to experience primary postpartum hemorrhage (4% vs. 0%). In contrast, women over 30 were more likely to develop postpartum hemorrhage (PPH),

with 8% experiencing secondary PPH. Proteinuria was common in both groups (60% in younger women and 54% in older women), reflecting a similar risk of kidney involvement, but there was no significant difference in the combined occurrence of proteinuria with other complications like de-ranged liver and kidney function tests (Figure 3.2).

Figure 2: Comparison of symptoms in two groups

The rate of cesarean deliveries was higher among younger women (74% vs. 48%), but the difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.865$), suggesting that both age groups have high rates of surgical intervention during delivery.

Premature rupture of membranes (PROM) was also slightly more frequent in younger women (66% vs. 52%, $p=0.624$), although this did not reach statistical significance either. Regarding neonatal outcomes (Table 3.2), the data reveal concerning trends for younger mothers. Neonatal deaths were

significantly higher among infants born to women under 19 (14% vs. 4%, $p=0.24$), although this was not statistically significant, possibly due to the small sample size.

The incidence of low birth weight (<2,500 g) was higher among younger women (50% vs. 36%, $p=0.247$), indicating poorer fetal growth outcomes in this group. Small-for-gestational-age (SGA) infants were more common among younger women (24% vs. 4%), suggesting that these pregnancies may be associated with fetal growth restrictions.

Figure 3: Comparison of weight and length of neonates between two groups

Interestingly, the Apgar scores in the first minute after birth were slightly lower among infants born to younger mothers, indicating possible immediate postnatal distress. Younger women had an Apgar score of 7.06 ± 1.09 , while older women had a score of 7.12 ± 1.04 , and although the difference was very small, it was statistically significant ($p=0.00001$). The NICU admission rate was also slightly higher for infants of younger mothers (50% vs. 42%), reflecting the higher rate of complications in this group, though the difference wasn't statistically significant ($p=0.493$).

In terms of other neonatal complications, asphyxia occurred more frequently among infants born to older mothers (20% vs. 12%), and preterm births were slightly more common in women over 30 (40% vs. 36%). However, neither of these parameters reached statistical significance, suggesting that both age groups face significant risks, albeit in different aspects of maternal and neonatal health. The table 3.3 compares religion, education, occupation,

and contraceptive use among women under 19 and over 30 years. In terms of religion, both groups had a nearly equal distribution between Hinduism and Islam, with no significant difference ($p=0.675$ for women under 19 and $p=0.223$ for women over 30). Regarding education, younger women had a higher proportion with no education (16 vs. 12), while older women had slightly more with higher education (12 vs. 8), but the differences were not statistically significant ($p=0.131$ and $p=0.473$, respectively). For occupation, a larger percentage of younger women were involved in skilled labor (42% vs. 34%), while older women had a higher proportion in business (20% vs. 6%), but again, the differences were not significant ($p=0.339$ and $p=0.79$).

Lastly, contraceptive use was more common among women over 30 (28 vs. 15), but this was not statistically significant either ($p=0.361$ and $p=0.417$). Overall, while some trends are observable, none of the differences between the groups reached statistical significance.

Table 3: Comparison of Sociodemographic Characteristics and Health Behaviors among Women under 19 and Over 30 Years

Groups	Parameter	Women <19yrs	Women >30yrs	Total	P value
Religion	Hinduism	27	26	50	0.675
	Islam	23	24	50	0.223
Education	Higher	8	12	50	0.131 (Pearson Chi-Square)
	No Education	16	12	50	0.473 (Pearson Chi-Square)
	Primary	14	14	50	
	Secondary	12	12	50	
Occupation	Business	3	10	50	0.339 (Pearson Chi-Square)
	Housewife	16	16	50	0.79 (Pearson Chi-Square)
	Professional	1	4	50	
	Skilled Labor	21	17	50	
	Unemployed	9	3	50	
Contraceptive Use	No	35	22	50	0.361 (Pearson Chi-Square)
	Yes	15	28	50	0.417 (Pearson Chi-Square)

Discussion

The primary goal of this study is to analyze the pregnancy rates in two distinct groups: adolescent and older women. A key focus is on maternal complications during pregnancy, labor, and delivery in both teenage and elderly first-time mothers. Maternal complications include hypertension (preeclampsia), gestational diabetes, and preterm labor.

Additionally, the study assesses fetal outcomes such as birth weight, gestational age, and neonatal health in both groups. By comparing these groups, researchers aim to identify any differences or similarities in pregnancy risks and outcomes across different ages. The average age in the teenage group (<19 years) was 16.82 years, while in the older group (>30 years), it was 33.6 years. Pregnant teenagers may face unique challenges, including

insufficient prenatal care and higher risks of preterm birth and low birth weight due to physiological immaturity and socioeconomic factors. In contrast, older mothers may have higher risks of gestational diabetes, hypertension, and cesarean deliveries. However, this study found no statistically significant difference in maternal age between the two groups ($p=0.589$), suggesting age alone may not significantly impact certain outcomes. In India, teenage pregnancy rates dropped from 16% in 2006 to 7.9% in 2016 due to improved reproductive health education. The prevalence of pregnancies among women over 30 years, also known as advanced maternal age, was reported at 23% in the U.S. and 4.5% in India [19-21]. All women under 19 were experiencing their first pregnancy (primigravida), compared to only 4% of women over 30. Primigravida in teenagers is associated with higher risks due to limited

knowledge of prenatal care and access to healthcare, while older women, particularly those who have had multiple pregnancies, may face complications from previous pregnancies. A significant difference ($p=0.00006$) in gravida status was found between the two groups, which may influence health outcomes. Previous studies found that older primigravida women had higher rates of pregnancy complications [22]. Blood pressure is a key factor in pregnancy outcomes. This study found higher systolic blood pressure in teenagers compared to older women (163.40 ± 16.7 vs. 144.40 ± 24.5 mmHg) and slightly lower diastolic pressure (87.60 ± 14.9 vs. 96.50 ± 9.3 mmHg). These differences, however, were not statistically significant ($p=0.62$ and $p=0.804$). Although preeclampsia was more common among teenagers in a previous study [23, 24], further research is needed to fully understand the relationship between blood pressure and age in pregnancy.

A higher percentage of women over 30 were married compared to teenagers (96% vs. 82%), though this was not statistically significant ($p=0.238$). Additionally, a slightly higher percentage of teenagers lived in rural areas (76%) compared to older women (64%), but this difference was also not significant ($p=0.255$). Socioeconomic status, access to healthcare, and education could influence maternal health outcomes, with rural teenagers having less access to healthcare services [25-28]. Teenagers had slightly lower hemoglobin levels than older women (8.78 ± 1.09 vs. 9.44 ± 1.7 g/dL), but this difference was not significant ($p=0.213$). Anemia during pregnancy, linked to poor maternal and fetal outcomes, was observed in both groups, suggesting the need for improved prenatal nutrition and care.

Religious affiliation between Hindu and Muslim participants was evenly distributed across both age groups, with no significant differences ($p=0.675$ and $p=0.223$) [29]. Educational levels and employment status showed no significant differences between the two groups. However, contraceptive use was higher in older mothers ($p=0.361$ and $p=0.417$). Women delaying parenthood for education and career were more likely to face fertility issues [30-33]. Older women had higher rates of eclampsia (10% vs. 4%, $p=0.008$) and cesarean sections, indicating potential age-related differences in complications like hypertensive disorders. Pedal edema, ascites, and premature rupture of membranes varied between the groups, further highlighting the complex relationship between maternal age and health outcomes. There were no significant differences in fetal heart rate ($p=0.883$) or gestational age ($p=0.897$) between the two groups, indicating similar intrauterine conditions. However, fetal heart rates averaged slightly higher in older women

(124.9 vs. 121 bpm). Emotional stress during pregnancy may influence fetal heart rate patterns [34]. While neonatal weight and length were not significantly different between the groups ($p=0.247$ and $p=0.113$), low birth weight was more common among teenagers (50%) compared to older women (36%). This suggests that factors beyond maternal age, such as prenatal care, could influence birth weight outcomes. Previous studies have also noted that neonatal weight increases with maternal age up to a certain point, after which the risk of low birth weight rises [35,36].

Neonatal mortality was higher in teenagers (14% vs. 4%, $p=0.24$), though this was not statistically significant. Other factors, such as preterm birth ($p=0.193$) and NICU admissions ($p=0.493$), showed some variation between the groups. Apgar scores were significantly lower in babies born to teenagers ($p=0.00001$), highlighting a potential age-related impact on neonatal health outcomes [37-42]. The study revealed no significant differences in neonatal outcomes such as birth weight, length, and mortality between the two groups. However, teenagers exhibited a higher incidence of low birth weight and neonatal mortality, although these differences were not statistically significant [41-44].

In conclusion, while age-related differences in maternal and neonatal outcomes were observed in both groups, many were not statistically significant. Factors such as access to healthcare, socioeconomic status, and prenatal care play critical roles in determining pregnancy and neonatal outcomes. Further research is needed to explore the complex relationships between maternal age, health status, and socioeconomic factors.

Conclusion:

The study highlights the distinct maternal and neonatal risks associated with adolescent and older primigravidas. Adolescents, due to their physiological immaturity and socioeconomic challenges, face higher risks of preterm labor, low birth weight, and neonatal mortality. They also exhibit a higher incidence of hypertensive disorders like preeclampsia. In contrast, older mothers, though better equipped socioeconomically and educationally, are more prone to gestational diabetes, hypertension, and cesarean deliveries. Despite the variances in specific health risks between the two age groups, both adolescent and older primigravidas require specialized antenatal care to mitigate complications. The study underscores the need for targeted interventions. Adolescents require more attention to prevent preterm births and improve neonatal outcomes, while older mothers need monitoring for gestational hypertension and diabetes. The findings emphasize that healthcare providers should not generalize

maternal care based on age but should adopt individualized care strategies. Furthermore, the significant differences in neonatal mortality and morbidity between the two groups—higher in adolescents—highlight the importance of timely medical intervention and access to quality healthcare, particularly in rural areas where these risks are often magnified. Addressing social determinants like education, healthcare access, and economic stability could further reduce adverse outcomes in both groups. Ultimately, this research reinforces that age-related risk factors should be a critical consideration in maternal healthcare. A more nuanced approach, factoring in the unique needs of both adolescent and older primigravidas, will be crucial in improving maternal and neonatal health outcomes, ensuring safer pregnancies, and healthier babies.

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